

HELPDESK RESPONSE 230

Rapid Scan on Early Learner Classroom Observation and Teacher Performance Tool Design and Deployment in Low-Resource Settings

Date June 2026

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DOI 10.53832/edtechhub.1229

About this document

Recommended citation Mufti, A., Handigol, A., & Ramesh Vasudevan, S. (2026). *Rapid Scan on Early Learner Classroom Observation and Teacher Performance Tool Design and Deployment in Low-Resource Settings* [Helpdesk Response 230]. EdTech Hub. <https://doi.org/10.53832/edtechhub.1229>. Available at <https://docs.edtechhub.org/lib/QKWCDTQK>. Available under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ALCOT	Active Learning Classroom Observation Tool
CFU	Checks for understanding
CLASS®	Classroom Assessment Scoring System
CMOT	Classroom Management Observation Tool
CSCOT	Communication Supporting Classroom Observation Tool
EGRA	Early Grade Reading Assessment
LOI	Language of instruction
MCOP2	Mathematics Classroom Observation Protocol for Practices
MET	Measures of Effective Teaching
MoE	Ministry of Education
MQI	Mathematical Quality of Instruction
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
SDI	Specially Designed Instruction

1. Background

The World Bank Group requested technical support from EdTech Hub to strengthen early grade teacher training and school-level supervision in Yemen. The Ministry of Education (MoE) in Yemen recently revised its teacher support tools, originally developed in partnership with Save the Children, and is seeking to align them with the country's formal supervision system. This system has been largely non-functional over the past decade due to conflict and resource constraints. Current teacher training content continues to follow the original Save the Children pathway and includes modules on psychosocial support, literacy, numeracy, and classroom management, with additional content increasingly incorporated to address contextual needs, such as remedial reading and mathematics.

Against this backdrop, the World Bank Group requested support from EdTech Hub to document and refine good practices in classroom observation tool design, teacher training content, and deployment approaches, and to generate practical, actionable guidance for near-term implementation. In response, this topic brief provides a review of best practices in classroom observation tools, covering both tool content and implementation models. The brief is based on a desk review of classroom observation tools used to collect data in contexts comparable to Yemen and includes a review of relevant World Bank documentation on the current tool, as well as additional materials and resources shared by Save the Children. The aim of collecting data on teaching practices through observation tools is to evaluate the efficacy of training provided to teachers in pedagogy and foundational literacy, and to enable pedagogical advisors to provide feedback to teachers.

Classroom observation tools are structured instruments designed to measure the quality of teaching practices, classroom interactions, and time management. For early learners, these tools play a crucial role in moving beyond simple checklists of infrastructure, such as whether a teacher has a chalkboard, to capturing the daily interactions that drive foundational learning in young students ([↑Molina et al., 2018b](#); [↑Pouezevara et al., 2016](#)).

This rapid scan is divided into three sections. First, [Section 2](#) presents the key theoretical principles to consider when developing or assessing the effectiveness of classroom observation tools. [Section 3](#) provides examples of several widely used, evidence-based tools, their inception, key features, implementation best practices, and evidence of effectiveness. Finally, [Section 4](#) provides a review of the key classroom observation tools

developed and tested by the World Bank to support teachers in Yemen on general pedagogy and teaching literacy. The review of the tools is grounded in literature on the key principles mentioned in this document. The rapid scan aims to lay the foundation for recommended revisions to the observation tools and their implementation in Yemen, ensuring that the suggested revisions are based on theoretical evidence and the practical experience of implementing similar tools in comparable contexts.

2. Design principles for a classroom observation tool

Based on recent literature, several best practices for designing classroom observation tools have emerged. These practices emphasise clear tool architecture, separating evidence from judgement, and integrating the physical learning environment and inclusion principles. The following are key principles to consider when designing or evaluating a classroom observation tool.

2.1 Ensuring validity, reliability, and measurement strength

Rather than focusing solely on scoring rubrics, best practice involves creating specific templates for collecting evidence independently of rating. This includes scripting templates for recording direct quotes and specific behaviours before any judgement is made, which helps prevent observer bias or ‘rater drift’. The tool should also provide shorthand codes (e.g., ‘CFU’ for Checks for Understanding) to tag evidence in real time, facilitating accurate sorting and scoring after a lesson ([↑Archer et al., 2016](#)). Enforcing a ‘collect now, rate later’ workflow can help reduce cognitive load and improve objectivity.

2.2 Pedagogical relevance

Traditional observation tools often treat the classroom environment as a neutral backdrop. New frameworks, such as the Active Learning Classroom Observation Tool (ALCOT), recommend explicitly linking pedagogy to physical space. This includes incorporating a classroom ‘blueprint’ section where observers map how the teacher uses space, such as movement zones or sightlines, to support or hinder active learning. The rubric should assess how teachers leverage specific features (e.g., flexible furniture, technology, or displays) to enhance learning, rather than just noting their presence ([↑Birdwell et al., 2016](#)). Tools should be designed to capture precise learning activities.

Best practices include validating observation tools by correlating their scores with standardised assessments such as the Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA). For example, Malawi’s Early Grade Reading Assessment observation tool differentiates ‘Teaching Phonics’ (e.g., modelling letter sounds and blending/segmenting) from ‘Teaching

Reading' (e.g., predicting from titles and asking comprehension questions) to assess instructional quality ([↑Pouezevara et al., 2016](#)). In Nigeria, observation-based 'lesson implementation scores' were statistically linked to students' gains in letter-sound identification, supporting the tool's reliability for monitoring progress ([↑Pouezevara et al., 2016](#)).

Effective tools assess not only the presence of print materials but also student interaction with them. For instance, Tangerine: Tutor and the Stallings classroom snapshot check whether students have direct access to books (e.g., one book per student) and whether they actively engage with these materials during lessons ([↑Newman et al., 2022](#); [↑Pouezevara et al., 2016](#); [↑World Bank Group, 2015](#)).

2.3 Ensuring standardisation across users

It is critical that a tool's different users view, understand, and measure the constructs consistently to ensure standardisation across data. An effective observation tool should include the necessary support materials to ensure this standardisation across users. For example, a well-defined tool integrates a 'Master Coded' video library as part of its core design, not just training. This library anchors definitions of 'Low', 'Medium', and 'High' performance with pre-scored videos that illustrate the constructs more precisely than text alone. The development process should also produce 'rangefinder' videos showing borderline cases between scores to clarify scale boundaries and improve scoring consistency ([↑Archer et al., 2016](#)).

2.4 Defining a clear focus

For coaching-focused tools (e.g., Tangerine: Tutor), embedding immediate data visualisation is key. Digital versions should include logic that flags low-scoring areas right after observation to guide feedback sessions. Automatically generated visual outputs, such as time-use graphs, can help shift discussions from subjective opinions to objective, data-driven conversations with teachers ([↑Pouezevara et al., 2016](#)).

For summative system monitoring, protocols should include unannounced visits to capture typical teaching practices, rather than the atypical 'show' lessons often seen during announced visits. Observation tools must support differentiated tracks that distinguish formative (developmental) from summative (evaluative) purposes to ensure appropriate use and interpretation of data. Additionally, tools should accommodate varying levels of teacher experience by focusing on classroom management and

basic instruction for novices, while also emphasising self-reflection and complex objectives for experienced teachers. A one-size-fits-all design may hinder growth by failing to address diverse developmental needs across career stages ([↑Alshehri, 2019](#)).

2.4 Contextual alignment

Research comparing tools such as Specially Designed Instruction (SDI), the Stallings classroom snapshot, CLASS® (Classroom Assessment Scoring System), and Teach shows that domains that appear distinct in theory often overlap when tested with real data. As a result, a common best practice is to use factor analysis methods (e.g., Principal Component Analysis) to assess whether the proposed domains function as distinct dimensions in the local context. These methods help simplify complex datasets by grouping related variables while preserving most of the original information. Designing tools with fewer, clearer dimensions can improve usability and robustness, as complex multi-domain frameworks often exhibit strong correlations between dimensions. Additionally, separating teacher effort (actions) from structural factors (school infrastructure) can prevent conflating teaching quality with environmental conditions ([↑Filmer et al., 2020](#)). In multilingual settings, minute-by-minute tracking of the language of instruction (LOI) is essential. Studies in Mali and Senegal found that the proportion of mother-tongue versus official-language use during reading lessons predicted student reading fluency outcomes ([↑Pouezevara et al., 2016](#)).

3. Examples of global and national classroom observation tools

This section provides a review and summary of various tested and scaled classroom observation tools that align with the objectives of the classroom observation tools developed by the World Bank for use in Yemen. The examples in [Tables 1](#) and [2](#) below provide an important reference point for reviewing observation tools currently used in Yemen, as they can help identify evidence-based design features, implementation lessons, contextualisation processes, and the effectiveness of these tools. Drawing on these lessons can support Yemen's MoE in refining its tools to improve instructional quality, ensure consistent supervision, and better link observations to teacher professional development.

Table 1. Comparative analysis of general pedagogical classroom observation tools

Tool, overview, and key features	Implementation requirements	Evidence of effectiveness
<p>Teach Primary* An open-access tool developed by the World Bank First edition launched in 2019; Second edition (focusing on inclusion) released in 2021 Available in Arabic, English, French, Portuguese, Russian, Spanish, and Swahili Tech required: tool can be administered using paper and pencil or an electronic data collection app; toolkit includes software for data collection & analysis Includes focus on: Time on Task: Uses three ‘snapshots’ (1–10 second scans) to record if the teacher is providing a learning activity and if students are on task Classroom culture: Supportive learning environment, positive behavioural expectations Instruction: Lesson facilitation, checks for understanding, feedback, and critical thinking Socioemotional skills: Autonomy, perseverance, social & collaborative skills Checklist to assess structural quality/inclusion (e.g., accessibility, lighting, materials) URL: https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/education/brief/teach-helping-countries-track-and-improve-teaching-quality Sources: †Molina et al., 2018a; †Molina et al., 2018b; †Molina & Pushparatnam, 2023; †World Bank Group, 2022</p>	<p>Training: Requires a 4-day training programme. The training material developed for the tool includes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A comprehensive manual with a rubric and user guide 2. Repository of classroom videos from different countries 3. Guides on developing the training content and master codes 4. Guidelines to record classroom videos for training 5. Source code to help analyse the results of the rated reliability test conducted at the end of each training <p>Certification: Observers must pass a reliability exam (coding video segments within one point of master codes)</p> <p>The tool recommends using local video footage during training to anchor the tool in the local setting</p>	<p>Validation: Validated in diverse contexts, including Mozambique, Pakistan, the Philippines, and Uruguay Impact: In Punjab, Pakistan, higher Teach Primary scores were associated with a 0.06–0.12 standard deviation increase in student test scores Psychometrics: Item Response Theory analysis confirms the tool effectively differentiates between teachers of similar ability</p>
<p><i>*There are three versions of the Teach tool: Teach ECE, Teach Primary, and Teach Secondary. In the context of this review, only Teach Primary is relevant and referred to.</i></p>		

Tool, overview, and key features	Implementation requirements	Evidence of effectiveness
<p>CLASS® (Classroom Assessment Scoring System)</p> <p>A proprietary & costly tool developed by the University of Virginia. Requires purchasing manuals & training. Kindergarten to Grade 3 Manual published in 2008</p> <p>Available in English and Spanish with adaptations in Chinese</p> <p>Tech required: Video recording for rigorous coding and reliability checks by trained raters</p> <p>Includes focus on:</p> <p>Emotional support: Positive climate, negative climate, teacher sensitivity, regard for student perspectives</p> <p>Classroom organisation: Behaviour management, productivity, instructional learning formats.</p> <p>Instructional support: Concept development, quality of feedback, language modelling</p> <p>Student engagement: Degree of student focus and participation</p> <p>URL: https://teachstone.com/class-observation-training/</p> <p>Sources: †Filmer et al., 2020; †Molina et al., 2018b; †Teachstone, no date</p>	<p>Training: Observers typically require 2 days of fee-based training plus practice to achieve reliability. The material available for the training includes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Observers manual 2. Scoring guides 3. Resource library with guides and videos 4. Recorded webinars on the tool and its application. <p>Certification: Raters must pass a certification test</p> <p>Scoring: Uses a 7-point scale (e.g., low, mid, high)</p> <p>Observation: Recommends 4–6 cycles of 20 minutes of observation, followed by 10 minutes for scoring</p>	<p>The Measures of Effective Teaching (MET) project of The Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation in the US found CLASS® scores predicted student achievement gains in maths and English</p> <p>Validated in Chile and Ecuador</p> <p>In some contexts (e.g., Afghanistan, Tanzania), reliability was lower, or scores were skewed toward the lower end, suggesting the need for adaptation</p>

Tool, overview, and key features	Implementation requirements	Evidence of effectiveness
<p>Stallings classroom snapshot</p> <p>An open-access tool developed by SRI International in the 1970s and adapted by the World Bank since 2002</p> <p>Language-neutral (codes interactions rather than content); manuals in English and Portuguese</p> <p>Tech required: Implementation via paper worksheets or electronic tablets</p> <p>Includes a snapshot grid to record participants, activities, and materials at 10 separate instances (e.g., every 3 or 5 minutes) during a class</p> <p>Includes focus on:</p> <p>Instruction: Reading aloud, demonstration/lecture, discussion, practice and drill, assignment/class work, copying</p> <p>Classroom management: Verbal instruction and discipline</p> <p>Engagement: students/teacher off-task, level of social interaction, time teacher is out of class</p> <p>Materials: Textbook, notebook, blackboard, learning aids, ICT</p> <p>URL: https://www.worldbank.org/en/programs/sief-trust-fund/brief/the-stallings-classroom-snapshot</p> <p>Sources:†Bruns et al., 2017b; Pouezevara et al., 2016; †World Bank Group, 2015; †World Bank Group, 2017b</p>	<p>Protocol: Observers must arrive before class starts. Observations occur at fixed intervals (e.g., every 3 or 5 minutes)</p> <p>Scanning: Observers must scan the room clockwise to record interactions at that precise moment</p> <p>Training: The low-inference nature allows for relatively shorter training than high-inference tools (approx. 5–10 days, depending on context). The following support materials are available for training on the tool:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Manual on observation methodology 2. Instructions on how to record the teacher and students' activities 3. Guide on data entry and interpretation 	<p>Reliability: High inter-rater reliability (>0.8) is achievable due to the tool's low-inference nature</p> <p>Correlation: Consistently correlates with student learning outcomes in Latin America and the United States; instructional time is a strong predictor of learning</p>

Tool, overview, and key features	Implementation requirements	Evidence of effectiveness
<p>Classroom observation tool for the first three grades in Arabic and mathematics</p> <p>An open-access tool developed by the Jordan Ministry of Education’s Supervision and Educational Training Department in 2020</p> <p>Available in Arabic; Tech required: Electronic administration via tablet, Excel for data analysis</p> <p>Includes focus on</p> <p>General pedagogical domains: Planning (lesson plans, sequencing, and time management); implementation (differentiated support, active learning, real-life connections); environment (psychosocial support, creativity, cognitive resources); learning for life (life skills, student self-learning responsibility)</p> <p>Subject-specific domains: Arabic, mathematics, other subjects (Islamic education and computer science, among others)</p> <p>Student performance checks: Random tests for three students during observation; checks for reading fluency or maths skills to validate teacher effectiveness</p> <p>URL:</p> <p>Source: ↑Jordan Ministry of Education, 2020 https://shared.rti.org/content/classroom-observation-tool-for-st-three-grades-arabic-and-mathematics</p>	<p>Supervisors verify teacher performance by testing students directly during lessons</p> <p>Mandatory post-observation conference for reflective questions and specific written recommendations</p> <p>The tool is adaptable based on student mastery: for example, it includes remedial worksheets for students with scores <40% and enrichment options for more advanced students. Assessors can create a fun, game-like atmosphere during student diagnostics to reduce anxiety</p> <p>Training: A detailed observation manual for the tool is available, providing a rubric for observers to score their observations on a 5-point scale</p>	<p>The tool is currently being implemented in Jordan, but its impact is yet to be studied</p>

Tool, overview, and key features	Implementation requirements	Evidence of effectiveness
<p>Classroom Management Observation Tool (CMOT)</p> <p>An open-access tool developed by the University of Connecticut. Published and validated in 2020</p> <p>Available in English</p> <p>Tech required: None (paper and pencil)</p> <p>Includes focus on</p> <p>Active supervision: Moving, scanning, and interacting</p> <p>Opportunities to respond (OTR): Academic questions/prompts</p> <p>Specific praise: Positive feedback contingent on behaviour</p> <p>Positive-to-corrective ratio: Ratio of positive feedback to corrections</p> <p>Supplemental checklist: Items for less frequent practices (e.g., posting expectations, classroom layout)</p> <p>URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339080154_Initial_Validation_of_the_Classroom_Management_Observation_Tool_CMOT</p> <p>Source: ↑Simonsen et al., 2020</p>	<p>Scoring: Items are rated on a 4-point Likert scale ('Disagree Strongly' to 'Agree Strongly')</p> <p>Usage: Designed for educational leaders (principals, coaches) to identify priorities for universal (Tier 1) professional development</p> <p>Focus: Brief, efficient observation of specific management behaviours rather than general pedagogy</p> <p>Training: No structured training materials have been found for this tool</p>	<p>Validity: Content validation by experts confirmed item relevance. Factor analysis supports a unidimensional structure (measuring classroom management)</p> <p>Reliability: Generalisability studies indicate sufficient reliability for specific items (e.g., active supervision) when used by a single rater</p>

Table 2. Comparative analysis of subject-specific classroom observation tools

Tool, overview, and key features	Implementation requirements	Evidence of effectiveness
<p>Communication Supporting Classroom Observation Tool (CSCOT) An open-access tool developed as part of the UK’s Better Communication Research Programme (BCRP) in 2012, followed by a feasibility study in 2015. Designed as a self-audit tool for teachers or for use by Special Educational Needs Coordinators/speech therapists to audit practice, with a particular target of the oral language environment of the classroom. Available in English Tech required: Can be used as a paper booklet or in an electronic version Includes focus on: Language learning environment (LLE): Physical environment and learning context (e.g., books, displays) Language learning opportunities (LLO): Structured opportunities to support language (e.g., small group work) Language learning interactions (LLI): How adults talk with children (e.g., using open questions, expanding on the child's speech) URL for online version: https://speechandlanguage.org.uk/educators-and-professionals/resource-library-for-educators/communication-supporting-classroom-observation-tool-cscot/ URL for paper version: https://express-licences.bristol.ac.uk/product/communication-supporting-classroom-observation-tool-cscot Source: †Law et al., 2019</p>	<p>Target: Children aged 4–7 Duration: Typically requires a one-hour observation of a morning teaching session Scoring: Proportion scores derived by dividing actual observations by total possible observations Training: No supplemental training material is available for the tool, but requests for additional information and/or any questions may be directed to Dr Ioanna Bakopoulou, University of Bristol See: https://www.bristol.ac.uk/people/person/ioanna-bakopoulou-1d8deb8c-8a8d-45f2-9a0c-d8a0bc5e6fda/</p>	<p>Sensitivity: Successfully discriminates between year groups Acceptability: Teachers reported the tool was easy to use and highlighted practice gaps, facilitating collaboration with speech therapists</p>

Tool, overview, and key features	Implementation requirements	Evidence of effectiveness
<p>Mathematical Quality of Instruction (MQI) Observation Instrument</p> <p>An observational tool developed by Dr Heather Hill in partnership with the University of Michigan and Harvard University in the mid-2000s</p> <p>Date: Observation instrument developed mid-2000s; coding rubric developed in 2006</p> <p>Available in English</p> <p>Tech required: Video recording; videotaped observations are necessary; training is video-based</p> <p>Includes focus on:</p> <p>Richness of mathematics: Student meaning-making and mathematical practices</p> <p>Errors and imprecision: Teacher's ability to use clear, correct, precise mathematical language and notation</p> <p>Working with students and mathematics: How the teacher interacts with students about content</p> <p>Student participation: Meaning-making and reasoning</p> <p>Explicitness & thoroughness: Detail and clarity of content</p> <p>URLs: http://drjennifersuh.onmason.com/wp-content/blogs.dir/1095/files/2016/02/MQI-4-Point-to-use-for-MATH-MODELING.pdf Coding rubric: http://sitemaker.umich.edu/lmt/files/lmt-mqi_description_of_codes.pdf Source: †Schoenfeld et al., 2018</p>	<p>Training: Requires raters to have strong content knowledge to detect mathematical nuances. Video-based training is available free online; the protocol is made available after completion of training & certification</p> <p>Scoring: Each dimension is scored for segments (e.g., 7.5 minutes) on a 1–3 scale (low, mid, high)</p> <p>Application: Used for research and teacher evaluation; focuses specifically on the content correctness and depth, unlike generic tools</p>	<p>Predictive validity: In the MET study, MQI scores were positively associated with student achievement gains</p> <p>Differentiation: Can distinguish between a 'well-managed' class and one with deep mathematical reasoning, where generic tools might fail to see the difference (e.g., giving a low score to a rote but orderly lesson)</p>

Tool, overview, and key features	Implementation requirements	Evidence of effectiveness
<p>Mathematics Classroom Observation Protocol for Practices (MCOP2)</p> <p>An open-access tool designed for use in K–16 maths classrooms; by Jim Gleason and Jeremy Zelkowski (University of Alabama) and Stefanie D. Livers (Missouri State University). If the tool is used to formally evaluate teachers' performances (e.g. for job evaluations or school administrative reviews), explicit consent must be obtained from the authors here.</p> <p>Date: The tool and descriptors manual were published in 2015, and a report on a validation study was published in 2017.</p> <p>Available in English</p> <p>Tech required: Paper rubric-based tool that can be used for live observations or with video</p> <p>Includes two subscales with 9 items each and focuses on:</p> <p>Teacher facilitation: Assesses how the teacher structures lessons and guides problem-solving, including key concepts, modelling, precise language, encouraging thinking, and responding to student questions</p> <p>Student engagement: Evaluates student involvement in math activities like exploration, using varied representations, critical thinking, perseverance, multiple solutions, and peer communication</p> <p>Scoring: Items rated 0–3 (0 = Not observed/no engagement; 3 = Regular, integral engagement)</p> <p>URLs: https://sites.ua.edu/jgleason/mcop2/</p> <p>Paper tool:</p>	<p>Recommended frequency: 3–6 observations for summative evaluation; single observations are only for formative assessment, not for full atmosphere assessment</p> <p>Protocol: Observers follow manual descriptors for reliability; observers should stay for the entirety of the lesson to account for structure and engagement; extensive training is not necessarily required beyond reviewing the detailed user guide</p> <p>Training: An observer's manual is available for training observers. No further additional support materials are available.</p>	<p>Validation: A validation study published in 2017 with feedback from 164 external experts confirmed content validity</p> <p>Reliability: The teacher facilitation subscale indicates high internal consistency; inter-rater reliability for subscales is in the 'good' range with minimal training</p> <p>Alignment: Aligns with national standards, emphasising conceptual understanding</p>

Tool, overview, and key features	Implementation requirements	Evidence of effectiveness
<p>https://bpb-us-e2.wpmucdn.com/sites.ua.edu/dist/f/482/files/2025/01/mcop%5E2_descriptors_short_02-29-2016.pdf</p> <p>Protocol descriptors and manual: https://bpb-us-e2.wpmucdn.com/sites.ua.edu/dist/f/482/files/2025/01/mcop%5E2_protocol_descriptors_2-16-2018_update_final.pdf</p> <p>Sources: ↑Gleason et al., 2015; ↑Gleason et al., 2017</p>		

4. Review of existing tools

Based on the principles defined in [Section 2](#), this section provides an overview of current classroom observation tools developed and implemented to support teachers in general pedagogy and literacy instruction in Yemen. Two classroom observation tools were reviewed as part of this assessment: a Revised Classroom Observation Form and an Enrichment Reading Session Classroom Observation Tool (see the [Annex](#)).

The Revised Classroom Observation Form is a general instrument for observing lessons designed to assess teachers' pedagogical skills across subjects. It focuses on five key domains—planning, direct teaching, communication with students, classroom management, and the class calendar—and includes 30 observable skills rated on a 5-point scale, with space to identify areas for improvement. In contrast, the Enrichment Reading Session Classroom Observation Tool is a subject-specific instrument designed for story-based reading lessons. It assesses 25 observable instructional practices using a three-point scale (not observed, partially observed, fully observed) and is intended to capture the quality of teacher practices during enrichment reading sessions. While both tools are designed for supervisors observing teachers during live lessons, the first provides broad, cross-subject coverage, while the second offers focused insight into literacy instruction.

4.1 Mapping existing tools to key principles

This section highlights the key areas of convergence and contrast between the two observation instruments, examining how each performs against the five core principles of quality classroom observation. It analyses their relative strengths and limitations in terms of technical robustness, pedagogical alignment, usability, clarity of purpose, and system fit. In addition, the section draws on selected international and national observation tools as benchmarks to illustrate how these principles have been operationalised effectively in other contexts. By referencing such examples, the analysis provides concrete illustrations of what strong design looks like in practice. This comparative perspective helps clarify not only where the current tools stand, but also how they can be strengthened to meet higher standards of validity, reliability, and instructional impact.

4.1.2 Technical quality (validity, reliability, measurement strength)

Both the Revised Classroom Observation Form and Enrichment Reading Session Classroom Observation Tool demonstrate strong face validity because the indicators they include closely align with widely recognised dimensions of effective teaching practice identified in established international teaching frameworks and classroom observation instruments. In other words, the tools appear to measure what they are intended to measure, as their focus areas—such as instructional quality, classroom management, and student engagement—are consistent with the core elements of effective teaching identified in the broader evidence base ([↑Molina et al., 2018b](#)). The Revised Classroom Observation Form captures broad domains of instruction, classroom management, and interaction, while the Enrichment Reading Session Classroom Observation Tool shows particularly strong content and construct validity for story-based reading instruction due to its tight alignment with the instructional sequence of an effective reading lesson.

However, both tools lack reliability as commonly associated with observation tools that do not include behaviourally anchored rating scales ([↑Kane & Staiger, 2012](#); [↑OECD, 2020a](#)). Neither tool includes behaviorally anchored descriptors to differentiate rating levels, leaving scoring vulnerable to subjective interpretation and inter-observer variation. In addition, the Revised Classroom Observation Form aggregates multiple constructs into a single summative score, which risks obscuring meaningful differences in teaching practice. The Enrichment Reading Session Classroom Observation Tool, while more granular, assigns equal weight to all indicators, despite evidence that some instructional practices are more strongly related to learning outcomes than others. Overall, both instruments are better suited for descriptive supervision than for high-stakes evaluation without additional reliability safeguards.

Figure 1. *The World Bank Teach Classroom Observation Tool*

The World Bank's Teach Primary Classroom Observation Tool ([↑World Bank Group, 2022](#)), reviewed in [Table 1](#), demonstrates strong content and construct validity, as its indicators are explicitly grounded in research on effective teaching practices and aligned with established frameworks of instructional quality. The tool uses behaviorally anchored indicators and structured observer training, which support high inter-rater reliability across contexts. The Teach Tool has been piloted and validated at scale

in multiple low- and middle-income countries, showing consistent measurement properties across diverse education systems. Its standardised design allows for reliable comparison across classrooms while retaining relevance for instructional improvement.

4.1.3 Pedagogical relevance (alignment with effective teaching and learning)

Pedagogically, both tools reflect sound principles of effective instruction as articulated in the literature on effective teaching and literacy instruction (↑[Béteille & Evans 2021](#)). The Revised Classroom Observation Form focuses on planning, active teaching strategies, a respectful classroom climate, and positive discipline, offering a holistic view of classroom quality across subjects. The Enrichment Reading Session Classroom Observation Tool, by contrast, includes deep instructional specificity, capturing pre-reading, during-reading, and post-reading practices that are well aligned with evidence-based literacy instruction.

Despite these strengths, both tools place greater emphasis on teacher actions than on direct evidence of student learning, a limitation frequently highlighted in reviews of checklist-based classroom observation systems (↑[Allen et al., 2013](#)). In the Revised Classroom Observation Form, student engagement and participation are largely inferred from teacher behaviour. In the Enrichment Reading Session Classroom Observation Tool, the focus is on whether instructional steps occur rather than on the quality of student responses or the depth of comprehension. Neither tool sufficiently captures differentiation for struggling learners or higher-order cognitive engagement. As a result, both instruments would benefit from stronger indicators related to student thinking, understanding, and learning progress.

Figure 2. *Examples of pedagogically relevant mechanisms in classroom observation tools*

The Stallings classroom snapshot is a good example of pedagogical relevance in measurement; it distinguishes between passive and active student engagement. The tool differentiates between “Reading Aloud” (teacher-led or choral) and “Practice & Drill” or “Discussion”, helping observers determine if students are truly decoding text or simply repeating in unison, which would be a less effective early grade practice (↑[Bruns et al., 2017](#); ↑[World Bank Group, 2017a](#)).

Another good example is the tool developed by Jordan's MoE. It requires supervisors to pause observations and randomly select three students to measure their reading fluency (syllables or words per minute) against grade-level standards. This confirms whether observed teaching translates into actual learning ([↑Jordan Ministry of Education, 2020](#)). Similarly, in Malawi, Primary Education Advisors test several students, as part of their classroom observation visit, post-lesson to guide feedback ([↑Pouezevara et al., 2016](#)).

4.1.4. Usability and feasibility

In terms of usability, both tools are designed for paper-based administration and align well with existing supervision practices, making them feasible in low-resource contexts, consistent with evidence on observation tool adoption in low- and middle-income countries ([↑Molina et al., 2018b](#); [↑OECD, 2020a](#)). The Revised Classroom Observation Form provides comprehensive coverage in a single instrument, while the Enrichment Reading Session Classroom Observation Tool supports real-time observation with a clear, lesson-aligned checklist.

However, both instruments impose notable demands on observers. The Revised Classroom Observation Form is lengthy and cognitively demanding during live observation, increasing the risk of superficial scoring. The Enrichment Reading Session Classroom Observation Tool, although more structured, includes a large number of indicators that can also strain observer attention, particularly during multiple observations. Neither tool is supported by a concise observer manual, which limits consistent use at scale. These usability constraints reduce effectiveness for frequent coaching visits.

Figure 3. *The Stallings classroom snapshot* ([↑World Bank Group, 2017a](#))

One good example of a pedagogically relevant tool is the Stallings classroom snapshot, reviewed in [Table 1](#). The tool has a strong focus on time on task and opportunities to learn, capturing how instructional time is actually used in classrooms. Systematically documenting teacher and student activities, the tool provides clear evidence of whether classrooms are engaged in learning-oriented practices rather than administrative or off-task behaviours. The tool is particularly valuable for diagnosing system-wide instructional efficiency, especially in contexts where maximising effective learning time is a key policy concern.

4.1.5 Purpose fit (coaching vs evaluation)

The two tools differ somewhat in their intended and practical use, but both exhibit tension between formative and evaluative purposes, reflecting a common challenge in teacher observation systems internationally ([↑OECD, 2020b](#)). The Revised Classroom Observation Form strongly signals an evaluative orientation through its emphasis on composite scores and performance categories, which may encourage compliance rather than reflective improvement. The Enrichment Reading Session Classroom Observation Tool is more naturally suited to formative coaching, as its indicators translate directly into actionable instructional feedback.

Nevertheless, the inclusion of overall effectiveness scores in both instruments introduces evaluative pressure and risks misalignment with their potential developmental value. Neither tool explicitly links observation results to structured follow-up actions such as coaching plans or professional development. Without clearer differentiation of purpose, both tools risk being underutilised as mechanisms for instructional improvement.

Figure 4. *The World Bank Coach Program*

The Coach Program, developed by the World Bank, outlines key considerations for designing a classroom observation tool tailored to coaching. The programme provides guidance on using a simplified, practice-focused observation tool, adapted from the TEACH Classroom Observation tools (Teach Primary, Teach Secondary, Teach ECE), to support formative feedback rather than evaluation. The adapted tool prioritises a small number of high-impact teaching practices, enabling coaches to observe, reflect, and support teachers through regular, low-stakes coaching cycles that are closely linked to professional development and classroom improvement ([↑World Bank Group, 2025](#)).

Tablet-based tools like Tangerine tutor incorporate decision trees that prompt coaches to address specific instructional gaps. For example, if an observer marks “No” for “Did the teacher model the activity?”, the system automatically suggests coaching on modelling techniques during feedback ([↑Pouezevara et al., 2016](#)). Tools like CMOT assess supervision through behaviours such as moving around the room, visually scanning students, and interacting with them ([↑Simonsen et al., 2020](#)).

4.1.6 Contextual and system alignment

Both observation tools are well aligned with Yemen’s education system, curriculum guidance, and supervision structures, a factor shown to increase feasibility and uptake of supervision tools at scale ([↑Molina et al., 2018b](#)). Their paper-based design, familiar formats, and emphasis on discipline, respect, and professional conduct enhance acceptability and feasibility within existing administrative arrangements. The Enrichment Reading Session Classroom Observation Tool further aligns closely with national literacy priorities and curriculum expectations for reading instruction.

However, strong system alignment also limits adaptability. Both tools provide limited flexibility for regional variation, evolving reform priorities, or diverse classroom contexts. Explicit attention to inclusion, learner diversity, and language background is minimal in both instruments. Additionally, their use as standalone observation forms—rather than as part of an integrated supervision and coaching cycle—reduces their potential to sustain instructional improvement.

Figure 5. *Examples of the Coach Program in Pakistan and Sierra Leone* ([↑Mufti, 2024](#))

Countries have adapted standardised classroom observation tools, such as the World Bank’s Teach Primary tool, by prioritising locally relevant teaching practices, simplifying indicators, and aligning them with national coaching and supervision systems. These contextualised tools reflect local curriculum goals, capacity constraints, and reform priorities, while retaining a common evidence-based foundation to improve instructional quality. Some country-level examples are available, such as **Punjab, Pakistan**, where the tool was shortened and focused on the most critical teaching practices identified through local data and stakeholder consultations, and tied directly into an instructional coaching model for school leaders. Similarly, **Sierra Leone** developed a locally contextualised observation framework based on a selected set of 11 teaching practices from the Teach tool, integrated with coaching by head teachers and district officers.

5. Conclusion

This section summarises the analysis of the two tools and identifies areas for improvement in future iterations.

5.1 Key strengths

- **Complementary coverage:** The two observation tools serve distinct but complementary purposes. One provides broad, system-level oversight of classroom practices, enabling supervisors to monitor general teaching quality across schools. The second offers deeper instructional insight, particularly in reading instruction, enabling more granular analysis of pedagogy and classroom practice. Together, they create a more holistic view of teaching quality than either tool could provide on its own.
- **Strong content alignment:** The indicators in both tools align with internationally recognised dimensions of effective teaching, including classroom management, lesson structure, student engagement, and instructional clarity. The Enrichment Reading Session Classroom Observation Tool also aligns with evidence-based early grade literacy pedagogy, including structured reading instruction and foundational skills development, thereby enhancing its technical credibility.
- **System fit and feasibility:** The paper-based format and familiar structure align well with existing supervision and inspection processes. This makes the tools easier to adopt and implement in low-resource contexts where digital infrastructure may be limited and where supervisors are already accustomed to similar formats. This alignment increases the likelihood of sustained use without requiring major system changes.
- **Instructional usefulness of the reading tool:** The Enrichment Reading Session Classroom Observation Tool is particularly strong in supporting concrete, practice-level feedback. It focuses on observable teaching practices related to early literacy instruction, making it easier for supervisors to provide targeted feedback that teachers can apply directly in the classroom. This is especially valuable in contexts where early-grade literacy outcomes are a national priority.

5.2 Key gaps

- **Weak reliability safeguards:** The tools currently lack behaviourally anchored rating descriptors, which can lead to inconsistent interpretation of scoring criteria across observers. Without clear definitions of what performance looks like at each rating level, scoring may be influenced by individual judgement, reducing comparability across schools, regions, and observers. This limits the usefulness of the tools for system-level monitoring and data-driven decision-making.
- **Limited focus on student learning:** Both tools place stronger emphasis on teacher actions (e.g., classroom management, lesson delivery, use of materials) than on cognitive engagement, evidence of student understanding, or learning progress. As a result, observations may capture whether teaching activities occurred, but not whether students actually learnt. Strengthening student-centred indicators would improve the tools' abilities to link classroom practice to learning outcomes.
- **High observer burden:** The length of the tools and the number of indicators increase the time required for observations and scoring. This can reduce observation quality, limit the number of classrooms supervisors can visit, and increase fatigue, leading to checklist-style completion rather than reflective observation. In practice, this may reduce both reliability and usefulness for coaching.
- **Unclear purpose:** The use of aggregate scores suggests a summative or evaluative purpose, while many indicators appear designed to support formative feedback. This dual purpose can create confusion among observers and teachers, potentially reducing trust and limiting the effectiveness of observations as a professional learning tool.
- **Limited follow-through:** There is currently no systematic mechanism linking observation results to coaching, teacher professional development, or instructional support. Without structured follow-up, observation data risks being underutilised and may not translate into improved classroom practice. Strengthening this connection would significantly increase the tools' impact on teaching quality.

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Annex

Revised Classroom Observation Form

Republic of Yemen
Ministry of Education
Sector of Curricula & Supervision
General Administration of Education
Supervision

الجمهورية اليمنية
وزارة التربية والتعليم

Curriculum and Educational Guidance
Sector
General Directorate of Educational

Classroom Observation Form

Elements	M	Criteria	Achieved to a degree				
			5	4	3	2	1
	1	Comprehensive quarterly/annual plan covering course topics and all elements					
Planning	2	The study plan is available					
	3	The objectives are varied, measurable, and observable.					
	4	Activities and methods are varied, engaging, and provide opportunities for learning.					
	5	The assessment is appropriate for the objectives, varied, and includes exercises that develop different learning skills.					
	6	Teaching strategies are varied and appropriate for the educational skills (reading, writing, expression, dictation, and arithmetic).					
			Total				
Teacher's direct teaching performance	1	Introduces the lesson in an interesting and engaging way for students.					
	2	Draws on their previous experiences.					
	3	Employ various educational activities (individual, pair, group, and class).					
	4	Uses activities that develop learning skills (reading, writing, reflection, speaking, listening) in light of the learners' abilities.					
	5	Employs educational tools.					
	6	Responds to students' questions and reinforces their answers.					
	7	Monitors students' work and activities in the classroom.					
	8	Employs interactive and active teaching methods and techniques.					
	9	Follows a logical sequence in presenting lesson elements.					
		Overall					
Communication and interaction	1	Uses correct, clear, and appropriate language.					
	2	Uses appropriate body language.					
	3	Communicates effectively with students to meet their specific needs and interests.					
		Total					
Classroom Management	1	The classroom environment is appropriate and safe for learning.					
	2	Uses professional records (attendance and absence).					
	3	Distributes responsibilities according to students' abilities and promotes their self-confidence.					
	4	Encourages students to express their opinions and freedom of expression, and calls them by their names.					
	5	Treats students with respect and without discrimination.					
	6	Uses positive discipline techniques and regulates relationships between students.					
	7	Manages the class in a positive manner, avoiding					

		verbal and physical punishment.					
	8	Helps students acquire positive attitudes and values.					
	9	Implements the classroom code of conduct.					
Elements	M	Criteria	Achieved				
			5	4	3	2	1
Class Calendar	1	Various methods, including observation, listening, and questioning.					
	2	Includes non-classroom activities (homework).					
	3	Provides feedback and uses a grade book for ongoing assessment.					
	Total						
Grand total							
Total form items: () Rating: ()							
Most important aspects of excellence: - - - - - - -				Points needing improvement: - - - - - - -			

Teacher's name: Signature:	Supervisor's name: Signature:	School principal's name: Signature:
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- Note: Grading scale:**
 - 1- Less than 50: Poor; 50 to 69: Average; 70 to 79: Good; 80 to 89: Very good; 90 to 100: Excellent.
 - 2- Final performance assessment score (150 divided by 1.5 = 100)

Enrichment Reading Session Classroom Observation Tool

Republic of Yemen

Ministry of Education

Sector of Curricula & Supervision

General Administration of Educational Supervision

Curriculum and Guidance
Sector

General Administration of
Educational Guidance

Enrichment Reading Session Note Card (Story)

Governorate	Directorate	School Code	Date of Visit	Visit Number

Teacher's Name	Grade	Story Title Level

Group	Reading Format			Level		Group
	Guided	Dual	Independent	Beginner	Intermediate	

Instructions for using the form

Three levels (scores) have been established to assess the availability of the indicator (2, 1, not observed) as follows:

- The column (not observed) means that the indicator is not available.
- Grade (1) means that the indicator is partially available.

Grade (2) means that the indicator is fully available.

M	Skill performance criteria	2	1	Not observed
■	Links objectives to content.			
■	Accurately identifies activities and teaching methods for enrichment reading.			
■	Selects the appropriate form of enrichment reading for the students' level (beginner – intermediate).			
■	Organizes students in a manner appropriate to the form of enrichment reading.			
■	Prepares students for the story using interesting introductions.			
■	Presents the title and cover image to anticipate the content of the story.			
■	Asks students to express their expectations based on their observations.			
■	Read the story expressively.			
■	Guide students to compare their expectations with what is written in the story.			
■	Relate the story to students' previous experiences.			
■	Pause while reading the story to ask students questions about their expectations or reactions.			
■	Explains unfamiliar vocabulary by comparing it to the picture, the context, related words, or antonyms.			
■	Moves on to the second page of the story after ensuring that the students have understood it.			
■	Ask students to summarize the content of the previous page.			
■	Ask appropriate questions to ensure understanding of the story's content.			
■	Vary the questions asked (recall questions, open-ended questions, closed questions (who, what, when, where, why), and extension questions).			
■	Enables students to read the story aloud when using guided, paired, and independent reading formats.			
■	Guides students to correct their own mistakes while reading stories.			
■	Ensures that students read the story well and provides appropriate feedback.			
■	Employ effective and varied methods to motivate students.			
■	Analyzes the story into its components by drawing a map.			
■	Uses body language effectively.			
■	Closes the lesson with appropriate closing techniques.			
■	Gives students homework activities and assignments.			
■	Uses appropriate assessment methods.			

Total score		Total points earned	
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Overall average = total points earned / total points available x 100	Overall average		Level of effectiveness	
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M	Areas of excellence	Areas for improvement
1		
2		

Teacher's name	Name of supervisor	Name of school principal
Personal ID number	Personal ID number	Personal ID number
Signature	Signature	Signature